

Matching Metadata: Recommendations for the Digital Resources of the Corpus Vitrearum International

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Introduction

Context. The Corpus Vitrearum International (CVI) is an international project engaged in the **preservation, documentation and study of stained glass**. Coordinated efforts to document medieval glass originally emerged after WWII, and the project was instituted, as Corpus Vitrearum Medii Aevi (Corpus of Medieval Window Glass), in Amsterdam in 1952, during the seventeenth congress of the Comité International d'Histoire de l'Art (CIHA).² The project soon came under the patronage of the Union Académique Internationale (UAI). Currently, sixteen projects contribute to it: Austria, Belgium, Canada, Catalonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, and the USA. In 2016, the project expanded its remit down to the present day. The national committees of the CVI have successfully produced approximately 150 printed volumes. The Corpus Vitrearum International encourages reflection on retrodigitization, the interconnection of image databases in the CVI domain, and multimodal digital publications. To organise coherent action on these topics and give visibility to a common heritage, the CVI set up the Scientific Unit of Digital Resources in the Corpus Vitrearum (Digital Unit, DU). The result of the DU's monthly discussions in 2022 and 2023 on image databases and websites, this document aims to share experiences and best practices for building web archives³ and platforms that provide images of stained glass.

¹ This document is written on behalf of the Scientific Unit of Digital Resources in the Corpus Vitrearum. The authors would like to thank all members for their valuable contributions.

² For further information see Kurmann-Schwarz and Hérolde *passim*; Frodl-Kraft *passim*; Comité international d'histoire de l'art and Union Académique Internationale *passim*.

³ The term 'archive' is used here to include but not require web platforms to be intended for long-term preservation.

Fig. 1: Glass from Herkenrode Abbey (Limburg, Belgium), now in Lichfield Cathedral (Staffordshire, United Kingdom), sIV 2d, 1538. Soldier at the Resurrection. Picture: © KIK-IRPA, Brussels.

Best Practices. The following recommendations on metadata, licences, and software notwithstanding, it is recognised that each national project is shaped by its history, members, funding, research goals, and institutional backing. It is therefore not considered mandatory to restructure or revise existing data to align to these recommendations. In 2023, however, several national projects were faced with the need to **remodel** existing databases, **improve** their annotation processes, make additional data available, or build **new** web applications.⁴ The recommendations set out here aim to help in these processes, as the national projects work towards an internationally shared set of metadata.⁵ The authors intend this to be a living document, to be revised as new technologies and file formats emerge or central assumptions change.

Methodology. As a starting point, the DU **surveyed** the different sets of metadata and software solutions used across national projects. The resulting comparative chart (cf. Appendix 2) illustrates both overlaps and differences in the data collected in several national databases. Taking this as a basis, the group then discussed a previous effort to identify core metadata during a **2013 meeting** in Romont, Switzerland, as well as other national databases of which we had knowledge in order to better understand what has shaped digital Corpus Vitrearum projects in the past. Since the divergence in the comparative charts from 2013 *and* 2023 made clear that a single metadata standard was not feasible, the group focused on recommending ways to build image archives using **data that can be linked** – not

⁴ The DU also discussed efforts to shift publishing strategies from the original printed volumes to the digital realm. Even though some CVMA image archives include descriptions and bibliographies, the group decided to tackle digital publishing separately from the questions of metadata.

⁵ In case you need an overview of core terminology in the realm of digital data, Schweizerische Gesellschaft für Geschichte *et al.* provides a good introduction in German and French. A suitable equivalent in English was published as a dedicated glossary section in Pfothenhauer *et al.*

just to each other, but also to third-party repositories across technology, genre, and language divides. To this end, the group looked into previous attempts to unify diverse cultural heritage data, such as the LIDO format (ICOM-CIDOC LIDO Working Group *passim*), as well as Linked Open Data efforts, such as the Europeana Data Model (Europeana *passim*), and the Culture Graph Interchange Format (Bruns *et al. passim*).

Challenges to Consider

CVI. The image archives of the CVI's member countries face several project-inherent challenges that affect the data they provide.

- Participating projects cannot be expected to agree on a single, common language. Cooperation in the CVI is based on **three official languages** (English, French, and German), and diverse funding contexts often require the use of a different or additional official, national language.
- Choosing a single technical solution is not viable because the national databases of CVI members differ in their **individual requirements**. While some projects need their IT systems to cover a fully fledged museum workflow, others require a single technical platform that also makes provision for digital publishing built on top of an image archive.
- CVI image archives may differ in whether they are built around **image or object** records as central data points. At the same time, image-based archives will likely need a means of grouping images into objects, and object-based archives may need ways of dealing with different representations of the same object, including overviews of several windows side by side that represent several objects at the same time.
- Even seemingly simple considerations, like providing the creation date of a stained-glass window, may become **complex** in individual projects when, for example, a composite window contains parts that would need to be dated individually.
- Legal frameworks and **best practices for the digitisation of cultural heritage** differ from country to country. The CVMA Germany, for example, works on the basis of a guideline called "DFG-Praxisregeln 'Digitalisierung'" (Altenhöner *et al. passim*).

Research Data. Image archives in the cultural-heritage domain can be considered part of a wider research-data environment that has a number of general, well-established expectations.

- As providers of research data, the digital projects of CVI members may be measured against how much they conform to established principles: that their data is **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable, cf. Wilkinson *et al.*) and designed with CARE (collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics, cf. Carroll *et al.*).
- Images for art-historical research are expected to be of high quality, but web archives also need **web-compatible** image formats. In addition, institutions holding image rights may not want high-resolution images to be publicly available.

- Depending on the provider, hosting large numbers of high-quality images can be expensive, and ideally, research data **should remain available** even after funding runs out.
- In most IT systems, image files and their metadata are (at least partly) kept separate because the files are large and the data needs to be accessible in a database. Using **Internationalised Resource Identifiers (IRIs)** instead of file names, which do not travel well across operating systems, has become a prominent solution for keeping files and their data in sync.⁶ Critics argue, however, that IRIs do not automatically travel well across web domains if a data set has to move to a new location.
- In many countries, image archives are now expected to **federate their data** to national infrastructures or data aggregators. To make this work, requirements for how common data points such as locations and dates are provided need to be met.

Linked Open Data (LOD). LOD describes a framework for connecting data semantically across diverse resources using the Resource Description Framework (RDF), a standard model for data interchange on the Web.⁷ Observing common practices would enable the image archives of CVI members to make their data both interoperable and available in federated-content scenarios. LOD has strong support from major players in digital art history (such as the Rijksmuseum and the Getty Research Institute), academic infrastructure projects (like the European Open Science Cloud or the German NFDI), and the semantic web community (including Google and the W3C). As an example, one building block of an LOD strategy in art history can be the use of Iconclass (Iconclass *passim*), a shared digital vocabulary to annotate iconography independent of language-specific text labels.

⁶ As a durable alternative, the CVMA Germany uses TIFF images with embedded XMP metadata. This is, however, more cumbersome to maintain (see next section).

⁷ RDF is a [standard maintained by the W3C](#). For more details see Schweizerische Gesellschaft für Geschichte et al., or the more technology-centric text book on linked data by Heath and Bizer.

[https://iconclass.org/11H\(NICHOLAS\)1](https://iconclass.org/11H(NICHOLAS)1)

Fig. 2: Matching iconography (Saint Nicholas) annotated by the same identifier of an authority file (Iconclass) across LOD-aware image archives, even though each one uses a different text label. **Left:** Yoki (Émile Aebischer), Standesscheibe Freiburg, Frauenfeld, Regierungsgebäude, 1961. Object: © reproduced with permission. Image: [Vitrocentre Romont, Yves Eigenmann, Fribourg](#). **Middle:** Hl. Nikolaus, Elzach, Pfarrkirche St. Nikolaus, 1523/24. Image: [Andrea Gössel, CVMA Freiburg, CC BY-NC 4.0](#). **Right:** Sint Nicolaas, Pellerin & Cie., ca. 1902. Image: [Schenking van de heer F.G. Waller, Amsterdam, public domain](#).

- The idea of LOD is to connect federated resources by making them more machine-readable: each resource gets a persistent ID (i.e., a long-lasting reference URL); any data and metadata are available through RDF-compatible APIs; and those APIs express the data by referring to IDs from **authority files** and vocabularies that include labels instead of merely providing text strings.
- Following these principles also allows resources to be ingested into knowledge graphs, i.e., information systems that connect resources (or IDs) into a large **data network** using semantic relations.
- To provide a specific example, an LOD-aware image archive would not just provide the name of a saint depicted in a window, but also the corresponding ID in an authority file. This way, the data can be more easily connected to resources from **other providers** that may carry additional information on the same person using a different spelling.
- In addition to RDF data, image archives are often expected to provide **IIIF manifests** (International Image Interoperability Framework), which are required for dedicated digital-object viewers, and **LIDO** (Lightweight Information Describing Objects) files for aggregators with a focus on the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) sector. Both standards may be treated as additional serialisations of data rather than central storage formats.
- To improve the interoperability of an image archive, web applications should include **embedded metadata** in the header section of individual resource views. The goal

should be to embed the data in formats that, for example, Zotero can import and search engines such as Google can easily pick up.

Image and Data Formats

Image files. While RAW image formats provide a lot of detail for the photographs in the projects under consideration here, they lead to excessive file sizes and problems when software components happen to be incompatible with a specific camera model. If storage space is not an issue, the recommended image format is **TIFF**, because it is lossless, allows for colour management, supports 16-bit images, provides several options for storing metadata, and enjoys broad support from all common image processors. If this format is used, however, **JPEG** derivatives also need to be created and stored, because of the format's smaller file size and its widespread browser support. If storage space is an issue, the best alternative is to store JPEG files directly, although it should be noted that this format only supports a colour depth of up to 8 bits and may lead to file-compression artefacts when users zoom into images. For accurate but web-safe **colour management**, translating the image to an sRGB colour profile is a safe bet, since most end-users cannot be expected to work on calibrated monitors. To additionally cater to those who need fully accurate colour reproduction using the original photographer's colour profile, offering full-size, original TIFF images for download may be a better option than leaving the original colour profile in all derivatives of an image.

Future file formats. While JPEG has proven useful as a baseline format for photography on the web for years, other image formats have been developed to bring the lossless quality of TIFF files and the small footprint of JPEG closer together. Of these formats, JPEG2000 and JPEG XL have now largely lost the support of all major browsers, making them unsuitable replacements for JPEG. The most promising format (as of 2024) is **AVIF**: its compression quality is an improvement on other formats; it produces fewer compression artefacts, allows for a colour depth of up to 12 bits, and is supported by all major browsers. Since the last major browser (Microsoft Edge) only started to support the format in June 2023, transitioning image archives away from JPEG may soon turn out to be an option if all imaging components as well as all aggregators connected to the archive are able to work with the emerging file format. Betting on such a file format, however, requires careful consideration: a future revision of this living document may well come to an entirely different conclusion, since support for file formats may change dramatically over the next few years.

Data storage. There are **many possible ways to store metadata**, and each national project needs to decide which solution works best for its needs. The following list provides pros and cons for the formats that the DU has discussed, and several CVI member projects have opted to combine two of these models to avoid individual disadvantages:

1. **Metadata stored in the images**, usually in the form of XMP containers in TIFF or JPEG files. This option ensures that images and their metadata are always linked, but it requires one of the other solutions listed below to actually list and use the data in a web interface. Changes to the metadata need to be performed on the image files

themselves, and they then have to be re-populated to all dependent software solutions reading the metadata, which can be slow due to the size of image files.

2. **Relational database tables**, usually an SQL database. Many CVI projects use this option because it allows for relatively neat data tables, database queries are fast, and many content-management systems already provide metadata functionality to some degree. The disadvantage of this option is that it requires a well-designed data model from the start as it is less adaptable once in use: e.g., changing a single-entry field to a repetitive one is tricky. In addition, such systems need to implement ways of ensuring that the connections between image files and database records remain stable, for example by using IRIs.
3. **Triple stores or graph databases** like Neo4j. To our knowledge, this option has only been implemented in part in CVI member projects in the form of graphs built on top of data stored in relational databases. The benefit of triple stores or graph databases is that they are very fast, they allow for repetitions of metadata fields, and they can be queried directly from a user's browser without another active server component that needs to be continuously managed (in addition to the database itself). The downside is that such databases are less mature than relational ones, and the RDF data model they implement has a steeper learning curve. They also need IRIs to connect image and metadata, and many common requirements (like passing on data to aggregators, providing findable content for search engines, or good accessibility) actually do necessitate active server components.
4. **Metadata in text files**, usually as JSON or XML files. The benefit of such solutions is that text files can be easily edited, transformed, or put under version control due to their small size. Querying the entire dataset via web interfaces, however, can become excessively difficult, because this solution does not scale well to large amounts of data. As above, IRIs are required to keep images and metadata in sync, and the file structure can quite easily become problematic, because JSON and XML are standards, but the possible ways of listing metadata in them are not.

Software Stacks

Overview. Different software stacks are used by the CVI member image archives. The following list serves as a reference list of solutions that work well; it is not our intention to exclude other possible solutions. The primary concern of the software stack is to make images and metadata **available and findable** for users, and to allow for the manual or automated retrieval of research data through APIs. How the data is organised internally varies a lot across these implementations. Those that are based on relational databases, however, usually end up distributing the metadata fields outlined below across several interconnected tables such as images, objects, locations, and entities (or artists/workshops).

- **Semantic MediaWiki:** this open-source, wiki-like software provides an extensible base for image metadata and has the benefit of including not just a relational database but also a triple store with a SPARQL endpoint that can be used as an API. The CV Portugal has experience with this set-up.

- **FileMaker:** this database manager can be used as desktop software and provides intricate options to store data, create input forms, and export the database to various formats. To present the data online, however, additional software is needed. The CV Switzerland uses this kind of custom pipeline.
- **TYPO3:** this open-source enterprise content-management system provides editing workflows, flexible input forms, and means of presenting data online, but it should be set up by a developer. Image metadata can be read using ExifTool. The CVMA Germany plans to make its custom extensions available during 2023 and 2024 under the moniker 'Cultural Heritage Framework'.
- **Heurist and Nakala:** Heurist is a database and content-management system focused on humanities data. It includes setup wizards for various things such as faceted searches. The CV France additionally uses Nakala as its data repository.
- **iDAI.objects arachne:** Arachne is an object database that comes with a web frontend and several standard APIs. Its server requirements mean that it is tough to set up properly, but some cultural-heritage repositories use/provide the software.
- **CollectiveAccess:** a media-management software designed for cataloguing and publishing museum and archival collections. It is used by the CV Poland.
- **Custom software:** entirely custom software stacks can be risky because they have to be maintained by someone. The CV Belgium has had a good experience with the custom-built software adopted for the country's national cultural-heritage database.
- **Omeka:** a web publishing platform designed for the creation of online exhibits and collections. It enables cultural heritage institutions, museums, libraries, and archives to manage and present digital assets even without extensive technical expertise.
- **Arches:** a software platform designed for the creation and management of cultural-heritage inventories and information systems. Its focus is on spatially mapped resources, such as archaeological sites, historic buildings, landscapes, and museum collections.

Currently available image platforms. Across the members of the CVI, the following websites may provide an overview of the different online image platforms developed with the software stacks listed above.

- [The Belgian Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage](#) runs an online database with artworks and objects of Belgian cultural heritage. The link queries stained-glass images recorded in the database, but members of the Belgian Corpus Vitrearum also use additional public and non-public databases and resources for their research.
- [The Swiss vitrosearch](#) is a freely accessible database that publishes research data on glass art and the corresponding images. The database was created as a joint initiative of the Vitrocentre and the Vitromusée Romont and is operated by the Vitrocentre Romont.
- [The image archive of the German CVMA](#) is a database that publishes images as research results of the joint research project by the Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz and Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences.
- [Great Britain's CVMA portal](#) includes an online picture archive.

- [The Centre André-Chastel](#), a research centre specialised in art history, provides an image database of stained-glass research in **France**.
- [The Corpus Vitrearum Poland](#) provides an image archive of their project *The Stained Glass from the Years 1800–1945 in the Roman Catholic Churches of the Metropolises of Cracow and Przemyśl*.
- [The Corpus Vitrearum Portugal](#) is working towards a platform with a wide selection of data and information on stained glass in Portugal.

Metadata

Core and additional fields. The following set of metadata fields differentiates between two types of recommendations. The **core** fields should, if possible, be included in the databases of CVI member image archives in an effort to make the data interoperable and LOD-compatible. This does not mean, however, that each image or object record needs to have data in every field marked as 'core'. **Additional** fields, on the other hand, are commonly implemented across CVI member image archives and are listed here mainly to help kickstart new or to-be-revised digital projects. Their usefulness may depend on a national project's specific requirements: the properties covering object rights, for example, are marked as 'additional', since archives only dealing with medieval stained glass may not want the burden of recording this information, but projects covering more recent artworks and/or property rights, for example, will find them essential. To ease the workload, some of the fields listed below may best be filled automatically using data from other fields. A rights string, for example, is commonly composed of the photographer, the image-rights owner, and the name of the image licence. A detailed version of the following list, including RDF predicates, is provided as appendix 1.

General

1. Identifier (core)
2. Image or object title (core)
3. Object authority ID (additional)
4. Description (additional)
5. Genre (core)

Current and former location of object

6. Country (core)
7. Region or state (core)
8. City or town (core)
9. Building (core)
10. Building authority ID (core)
11. Latitude (core)
12. Longitude (core)

Window

13. Location in the building (core)
14. Position on plan (core)
15. Number (core)
16. Panel row (core)
17. Panel column (core)

Object rights

18. Owner (additional)
19. Copyright holder (additional)
20. Rights string (additional)
21. Licence name (additional)
22. Licence authority ID (additional)

Dimensions

23. Height (core)
24. Width (core)
25. Diameter (core)

Condition

26. Technique (additional)
27. Materials (additional)
28. Restoration history (additional)

Creation date

29. Start (core)
30. End (core)

Entity

31. Name (core)
32. Authority ID (additional)
33. Role (core)

Subject

34. Iconclass/iconography authority ID (core)
35. Iconclass/iconography keywords (additional)
36. Inscription (additional)
37. Signature (additional)

Image

38. Photographic process (additional)
39. Photographic context (additional)
40. Creation date (core)

Image rights

41. Photographer (core)
42. Owner (core)
43. Publisher (additional)
44. Rights string (additional)
45. Licence name (additional)
46. Licence authority ID (core)

Background

47. Related images or objects (additional)
48. Internal image or object notes (additional)
49. Image or object bibliography (additional)

Sample illustration. The following figure provides one possible implementation of the metadata suggestions listed above. It may be translated into a relational database, flat-file metadata, or a graph database depending on a project's individual requirements. This may prove especially useful for projects in need of an entirely new database.

Fig. 3: Visual outline of how the recommended metadata fields could be interconnected.

Other data models. The above list is supposed to provide a starting point for CVI projects building or remodelling their database. Another option is to use an **off-the-shelf** data model provided with the software you want to use. Data models based on LIDO and Europeana can usually be adapted to work with the above data points. The known **downsides** are that the five fields specific to window locations inside a building need to be combined into a single 'alternative title' and both models provide a vast set of fields to fill, which can be overwhelming compared to more focused data models.

Rights and Licensing

Legal framework. It is recommended that any possible legal issues surrounding cultural-heritage objects and photographs intended for publication be considered as early as possible. Regulations may differ from country to country and involve not just copyright but also cultural-heritage or ownership laws, so it may be useful to obtain legal counsel versed in the specifics of the country (or countries) involved. From the projects represented in the DU, six rights holders or legal areas should be considered: original artists, conservators, photographers, property owners, projects themselves, and (if applicable) heritage administrations. In addition, it may be useful to check with any publishers involved in the project whether they would print content that carries a specific licence.

Metadata licences. Reusing research data from image archives provided without any licence usually requires identifying and contacting original authors, possibly an unavailable corporate author, or even having to wait for copyright terms to be lifted. To avoid this hassle, it is recommended that metadata be published with a licence that is as open as possible and allows for reuse in as many contexts as possible. The **CC0** licence effectively releases the metadata into the public domain and is generally recommended if it agrees with the project's funding conditions and policy framework. Aggregators like Europeana only allow for the contribution of data that is in the public domain or carries a CC0 licence. If your metadata records have authors, for example, on account of their containing extensive descriptions or reusing existing text, the best alternative to CC0 is **CC BY**, which simply requires that the name of the author be mentioned when they are reused, in line with good academic practice. More restrictive licences that limit commercial use ("NC" or "non-commercial") or require reused content to be shared under the same licence ("SA" or "share alike") often effectively exclude the data from being used by projects and/or events that rely on commercial funding or predefined output licences, such as Wikidata or the Coding da Vinci hackathons, and should thus be avoided. In some cases, a different licence may be more in line with a country's specific legal framework.

Image licences. For images, the recommendation leans towards a **CC BY** licence. While CC0 lets anyone use the image any way they want, it also means that other researchers may encounter the image without any hint about how it was produced and whether it was manipulated, rendering it effectively useless if they cannot locate the original source. Using a CC BY licence requires attribution and thus a brief note about how and in what context the image was produced. If you choose such an attribution licence, however, you should make sure that your metadata includes a **credit string** that can be used to avoid confusion about whether "attribution" refers to the photographer, the project providing the image, a permalink, or an organisation/sponsor.

Missing Pieces

Desiderata. In compiling these recommendations, the following missing building blocks on the road to interconnected CVI member resources were identified. It may prove useful to work on these with the wider art history, digital humanities, and/or GLAM communities:

- There appears to be a need for pertinent **guidelines and best practices** on how to do research with digital (image) resources.
- **Mappings** (i.e., comparison charts listing equivalent data values) for IconClass, Getty AAT, Sancti, and possibly Wikidata could greatly improve the interoperability of existing iconography data.
- A federated **content search** across CVI resources may prove useful for art historians. This could facilitate existing integrations, aggregators, and knowledge graphs, but the interfaces might need to be adapted for the targeted audience to become more accessible than, for example, a SPARQL query.
- The DU does not yet have a lot of expertise in integrating 2D image archives with 3D data or annotating **3D data** directly, but some participating projects have expressed interest in experimenting with the technology.

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Appendix 1: Metadata in Detail

Relation to the CVI publication guidelines. The Corpus Vitrearum International has published official guidelines on how to describe stained glass in print volumes (cf. Comité international d'histoire de l'art and Union Académique Internationale *passim*). We have taken care to align our metadata fields recommended for digital resources with these original publication guidelines. In fact, the time and care invested into coordinating these guidelines enabled the Digital Unit to agree on ways to align metadata across web platforms.

RDF namespaces. The RDF predicates listed below need namespace URIs to properly identify each predicate in a Linked Open Data scenario. These namespaces and RDF predicates are compiled here for reference based on what is already being used across CVI projects.

- **aat:** <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/>
- **cvma:** <https://lod.academy/cvma/ns/xmp/>
- **dc:** <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>
- **dcmitype:** <http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/>
- **dcterms:** <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
- **edm:** <http://www.europeana.eu/schemas/edm/>
- **exif:** <http://ns.adobe.com/exif/1.0/>
- **Iptc4xmpExt:** <http://iptc.org/std/Iptc4xmpExt/2008-02-29/>
- **photoshop:** <http://ns.adobe.com/photoshop/1.0/>
- **xmp:** <http://ns.adobe.com/xap/1.0/>
- **xmpRights:** <http://ns.adobe.com/xap/1.0/rights/>

RDF entities. The metadata fields below provide properties that can be used to provide the field's information in RDF serialisations. Each entity (or class) that is described using these properties, however, should also be of a specific type. We recommend the use of the

authority file Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and/or DCMI types for this purpose: an object entity should have the type [aat:300311889](#) ('object') and/or [dcmitype:PhysicalObject](#) while an image of an object should be described as [aat:300312231](#) ('visual surrogate') and/or [dcmitype:Image](#). If you want to provide information on buildings, persons, workshops, and other entities, they should all be typed accordingly.

Fig. 4: From Herkenrode Abbey (Limburg, Belgium), now in Lichfield Cathedral (Staffordshire, United Kingdom), nIII 1a–c, 2a–c, 1532. Three nuns at prayer: Matilde, Aleyde and Marie de Lexhy. Matilde was abbess 1520–1548 and responsible for significant rebuilding works at the abbey. The nuns adore the Virgin and Christ Child on the left. Inbetween is a depiction of Matilde's abbey church, and the arms of Béatrice de Lobosch (abbess 1341–1354), long thought to have been responsible for significant reconstruction works during her abbacy. Image used to provide sample metadata throughout the list below. Picture: © KIK-IRPA, Brussels.

1.	Field	General: identifier	Core
	RDF	@id, dc:identifier	
	Value	URI	
	Example	No sample record online (yet)	
	Note	Can be used to uniquely identify a resource when combined with a repository identifier, such as a web URL. In Wikidata, for example, a complete @id is "https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q666960" with "Q666960" being the identifier.	

2.	Field	General: image or object title	Core
	RDF	dc:title	

Value	string
Example	Three nuns at prayer: Matilde, Aleyde and Marie de Lexhy
Note	This may be used twice in case the archive contains both image and object records, not just one of the two.

3.	Field	General: object authority ID	Additional
	RDF	dcterms:identifier	
	Value	URI	
	Example	<i>No sample record online (yet)</i>	
	Note	Space for authority URIs to identify an object in case you are including object data in the database. This can be helpful to identify the same object across multiple projects by using, for example, its Wikidata ID.	

4.	Field	General: description	Additional
	RDF	dc:description	
	Value	string	
	Example	Matilde was abbess 1520–1548 and responsible for significant rebuilding works at the abbey. The nuns adore the Virgin and Christ Child on the left. Inbetween is a depiction of Matilde's abbey church, and the arms of Béatrice de Lobosch (abbess 1341–1354), long thought to have been responsible for significant reconstruction works during her abbacy.	
	Note	Brief description of the image or object. This could be used as, for example, alternative text that visually impaired users require for images on the web. Producing descriptions, however, is resource-intensive. As a result, some CVI member projects use strings generated from Iconclass labels without a dedicated description field. Using machine learning to generate descriptions might become a viable alternative in the future, but this would require a highly specialised ML model.	

5.	Field	General: genre	Core
	RDF	dc:type	
	Value	URI or string (limited set)	
	Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300263722	

Note	Many aggregators and file formats, including LIDO, require this information. Using a limited set of URIs or linking a limited set of allowed strings to URIs is helpful for cross-language comparisons.
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6.	Field	Current and former location of object: country	Core
	RDF	edm:country , lptc4xmpExt:CountryName	
	Value	string	
	Example	United Kingdom	
	Example	Belgium	
	Note	Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure uniform country names. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

7.	Field	Current and former location of object: region or state	Core
	RDF	lptc4xmpExt:ProvinceState	
	Value	string	
	Example	Staffordshire	
	Example	Limburg	
	Note	Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure uniform region or state names. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

8.	Field	Current and former location of object: city or town	Core
	RDF	lptc4xmpExt:City	
	Value	string	
	Example	Lichfield	
	Example	Hasselt	
	Note	Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure uniform names of cities or towns. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

9.

Field	Current and former location of object: building	Core
RDF	edm:currentLocation , lptc4xmpExt:Sublocation , cvma:FormerLocation	
Value	string	
Example	Lichfield Cathedral	
Example	Herkenrode Abbey	
Note	Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure uniform names of buildings. Churches in particular may be named after current or historical dedications, with or without abbreviations, etc. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

10.

Field	Current and former location of object: building authority ID	Core
RDF	lptc4xmpExt:LocationId , cvma:FormerLocationIds	
Value	URI	
Example	http://viaf.org/viaf/127830403	
Example	https://id.erfgoed.net/erfgoedobjecten/22246	
Note	This refers to the URI of a Linked Open Data resource such as Geonames or Wikidata. Using these community platforms has the benefit of enabling the dynamic retrieval of labels in several languages and coordinates in different notations. In a streamlined annotation system, filling this field could auto-fill all other location fields. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

11.

Field	Current and former location of object: latitude	Core
RDF	exif:GPSLatitude	
Value	floating-point number	
Example	52.6855	
Example	50.956389	
Note	Usually refers to the building, but some buildings are so large that coordinates may be used more accurately for a particular part of the building. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

12.	Field	Current and former location of object: longitude	Core
	RDF	exif:GPSLongitude	
	Value	floating-point number	
	Example	-1.8303	
	Example	5.278889	
	Note	Usually refers to the building, but some buildings are so large that coordinates may be used more accurately for a particular part of the building. All location fields should be connected to image or object data in a way that makes clear whether you are referring to a current or a former location.	

13.	Field	Window: location in the building	Core
	RDF	cvma:PartOfBuilding	
	Value	string	
	Example	Lady Chapel	
	Note	Part of the building (architectural) that the window is located in.	

14.	Field	Window: position on plan	Core
	RDF	cvma:Direction	
	Value	string	
	Example	n	
	Note	Used in accordance with CVI publication guidelines. Only relevant for objects that are windows. Alternatively, some systems combine window direction and number with panel row and column into a single field that identifies a window, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.	

15.	Field	Window: number	Core
	RDF	cvma:Pane	
	Value	string	
	Example	III	

Note	Used in accordance with CVI publication guidelines. Only relevant for objects that are windows. Alternatively, some systems combine window direction and number with panel row and column into a single field that identifies a window, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.
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16.	Field	Window: panel row	Core
	RDF	cvma:Row	
	Value	string	
	Example	1-2	
	Note	Used in accordance with CVI publication guidelines. Only relevant for objects that are windows. Alternatively, some systems combine window direction and number with panel row and column into a single field that identifies a window, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.	

17.	Field	Window: panel column	Core
	RDF	cvma:Column	
	Value	string	
	Example	a-c	
	Note	Used in accordance with CVI publication guidelines. Only relevant for objects that are windows. Alternatively, some systems combine window direction and number with panel row and column into a single field that identifies a window, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.	

18.	Field	Object rights: owner	Additional
	RDF	dcterms:rightsHolder	
	Value	URI or string	
	Example	http://viaf.org/viaf/62147095006925080412	
	Note	Identifies the owner of the object for future reference. You may choose to keep this field hidden or even add a secret version of it in case not all owners you work with want to be identified publicly.	

19.	Field	Object rights: copyright holder	Additional
	RDF	dcterms:rightsHolder	

Value	URI or string
Example	<i>Not applicable</i>
Note	While this is labelled as an additional field, it is absolutely necessary as soon as you manage and/or publish data on objects under copyright.

20.	Field	Object rights: rights string	Additional
	RDF	dc:rights	
	Value	string	
	Example	Public domain	
	Note	Complete rights string to be used when object information needs to be provided on a website. This usually consists of the owner and/or copyright holder as well as the licence attached to the object, or simply a public-domain marker.	

21.	Field	Object rights: licence name	Additional
	RDF	Label of dc:license	
	Value	string (limited set)	
	Example	Public domain	
	Note	Short name of the licence of the object. Limiting the number of options helps filter out data on objects that should be kept private. Could be filled automatically based on the authority ID of a licence.	

22.	Field	Object rights: licence authority ID	Additional
	RDF	dc:license	
	Value	URI (limited set)	
	Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300055611	
	Note	Full web address of the licence of the object. Limiting the number of options helps filter out data on objects that should be kept private.	

23.	Field	Dimensions: height	Core
	RDF	cvma:ObjectHeight	
	Value	floating-point number	

Example	120
Note	Contains the height of the window. Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure that all values use the same unit of measurement, e.g. centimetres. Alternatively, some systems combine height, width, and diameter into a single field that provides a window's dimensions, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.

24.

Field	Dimensions: width	Core
RDF	cvma:ObjectWidth	
Value	floating-point number	
Example	210	
Note	Contains the width of the window. Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure that all values use the same unit of measurement, e.g. centimetres. Alternatively, some systems combine height, width, and diameter into a single field that provides a window's dimensions, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.	

25.

Field	Dimensions: diameter	Core
RDF	cvma:ObjectDiameter	
Value	floating-point number	
Example	<i>Not applicable</i>	
Note	Contains the diameter of a circular window. Make sure you have a recommendation in place to ensure that all values use the same unit of measurement, e.g. centimetres. Alternatively, some systems combine height, width, and diameter into a single field that provides a window's dimensions, but this may make it harder to retrieve relevant information and ensure a uniform format.	

26.

Field	Condition: technique	Additional
RDF	aat:300138082	
Value	URI or string (limited set)	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053058	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300241557	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053366	

Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053929
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300233397
Note	Many aggregators and file formats, including LIDO, recommend providing this information. Using a limited set of URIs (like Getty AAT) or linking a limited set of allowed strings to URIs is helpful for cross-language comparisons. It may be feasible to automatically retrieve this information based on the genre field.

27.

Field	Condition: materials	Additional
RDF	dcterms:medium	
Value	URI or string (limited set)	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300010797	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300010853	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011022	
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300343594	
Note	Many aggregators and file formats, including LIDO, recommend providing this information. Using a limited set of URIs (like Getty AAT) or linking a limited set of allowed strings to URIs is helpful for cross-language comparisons. It may be feasible to automatically retrieve this information based on the genre field.	

28.

Field	Condition: restoration history	Additional
RDF	cvma:RestorationHistory (comprehensive string), cvma:RestorationCircaDate (single-event string), cvma:RestorationDateStart (single-event date), cvma:RestorationDateEnd (single-event date), cvma:RestorationEvent (single-event string)	
Value	string or date-and-string combination	
Example	Late 19th century: stonework of the tracery modified by Sir George Gilbert Scott and his son John Oldrid Scott	
Example	1891-1892: glazing restored by Camm Brothers & Co	
Example	Ca. 1939-1945: glazing removed and repaired	
Example	January 2014-January 2015: some painted details were strengthened on the external face of the glass with cold paint by Barley Studio	

Note	Information about changes and alterations made to the object. This could take the form of a free-form text or, more ideally, structured data including at least a start date, an end date, and a description of a restoration event.
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29.

Field	Creation date: start	Core
RDF	cvma:AgeDeterminationStart	
Value	date	
Example	1532-01-01	
Note	Accurate date in the form “YYYY-MM-DD” that marks the beginning of the determined period when the object was created. Determining the age of a window can become particularly difficult for composite windows.	

30.

Field	Creation date: end	Core
RDF	cvma:AgeDeterminationEnd	
Value	date	
Example	1532-12-31	
Note	Accurate date in the form “YYYY-MM-DD” that marks the end of the determined period when the object was created. Determining the age of a window can become particularly difficult for composite windows.	

31.

Field	Entity: name	Core
RDF	cvma:EntityName	
Value	string	
Example	Sir George Gilbert Scott	
Example	John Oldrid Scott	
Example	Camm Brothers & Co	
Example	Barley Studio	
Note	May alternatively be realised as an “artist” or “workshop” field. Contains a human-readable name of the person or organisation you want to associate with an image or object record. If you provide entity information, it may be useful to add a hidden field to store names that you are not allowed to provide publicly.	

32.	Field	Entity: authority ID	Additional
	RDF	cvma:EntityIdentifier	
	Value	URI	
	Example	http://viaf.org/viaf/46909901	
	Example	http://viaf.org/viaf/15841311	
	Example	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q60289266	
	Example	http://viaf.org/viaf/297222376	
	Note	May alternatively be realised as an “artist” or “workshop” field. Compared to just providing the name, also giving an ID from an authority file has the benefit of adding labels in different languages, resolving variant spellings, and differentiating entities with the same name. Suitable authority files for people and organisations include VIAF, Wikidata, GND, and SIKART.	

33.	Field	Entity: role	Core
	RDF	cvma:EntityRole	
	Value	URI or string (limited set)	
	Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300102842	
	Note	Only useful if the previous two fields are not realised as “artist” or “workshop” fields. Here you may add a set of predefined options that entities may have in relation to the image or object record, such as “artist,” “representation,” “collector,” “donor,” or “conservator.”	

34.	Field	Subject: Iconclass/iconography authority ID	Core
	RDF	dc:subject , cvma:IconclassNotation	
	Value	URI or string	
	Example	11P31522(+5)	
	Example	11F41	
	Example	11Q712	
	Example	11Q712	

Example	46A122(LOBOSCH)1
Note	You may choose to use the full URI of an Iconclass or just the identifier: this is easier to read with multiple Iconclasses, and Iconclass identifiers can be 'read' by those in the know.

35.

Field	Subject: Iconclass/iconography keywords	Additional
RDF	cvma:IconclassDescription	
Value	string	
Example	Christian religion, Church, Roman Catholic Church, clergy, community, dignitary, functionary, monastery, monk, nun, occupations, order, organisation, religion, supernatural	
Example	Christ-child, Christian religion, Madonna (Mary with Christ-child), Mary (Virgin), half-length, religion, standing, supernatural	
Example	Christian religion, God, chapel, church, cult, exterior, liturgy, religion, supernatural	
Example	Chivalry, civilization, class, coat of arms, community, culture, heraldry, knighthood, nobility, patriciate, social stratification, society, stratification	
Note	Adding (or automatically importing) keywords associated with an Iconclass can help users searching your database or interconnecting your database records.	

36.

Field	Subject: inscription	Additional
RDF	aat:300028702	
Value	string	
Example	ANNO	
Example	1532	
Note	Provides inscriptions in the stained glass.	

37.

Field	Subject: signature	Additional
RDF	aat:300028705	
Value	string	
Example	<i>Not applicable</i>	
Note	Provides signatures in the stained glass.	

38.	Field	Image: photographic process	Additional
	RDF	cvma:PhotographicType , Iptc4xmpExt:DigitalSourceType	
	Value	string (limited set)	
	Example	Digital picture, transmitted light	
	Note	Provides info on the photographic process used to generate the digital representation of the image. Some CVI member archives have chosen to differentiate between a photographic process such as “transmitted light” and an image type such as “digital picture.” Limiting the set of options used here helps identify, for example, all images digitised from a photographic negative.	

39.	Field	Image: photographic context	Additional
	RDF	cvma:PhotographicContext	
	Value	string (limited set)	
	Example	Ex situ	
	Note	Provides info on the photographic context in which the photograph was produced. Limiting the number of available options for this field can be useful to keep your data on point.	

40.	Field	Image: creation date	Core
	RDF	dcterms:created , xmp:CreateDate	
	Value	date	
	Example	2015-01-31	
	Note	Date when the original photograph (not necessarily the digitised version) was produced.	

41.	Field	Image rights: photographer	Core
	RDF	dc:creator	
	Value	string	
	Example	Barley Studio	
	Note	Name of the photographer.	

42.	Field	Image rights: owner	Core
	RDF	dcterms:rightsHolder , xmpRights:Owner	
	Value	URI or string	
	Example	KIK-IRPA, Brussels	
	Note	Name of the owner of the digitised photograph.	

43.	Field	Image rights: publisher	Additional
	RDF	dc:publisher	
	Value	URI or string	
	Example	KIK-IRPA, Brussels	
	Note	Name of the publisher of the digitised photograph, usually the CVI member project, a particular office, or another image provider.	

44.	Field	Image rights: rights string	Additional
	RDF	dc:rights , photoshop:Credit	
	Value	string	
	Example	Images © Barley Studio, montage © KIK-IRPA, Brussels	
	Note	Complete rights string to be used when the image is reused. This often consists of the photographer, the owner, the publisher, and/or the licence attached to the image.	

45.	Field	Image rights: licence name	Additional
	RDF	Label of dc:license , xmpRights:UsageTerms	
	Value	string (limited set)	
	Example	Copyright	
	Note	Short name of the licence of the image, such as "CC BY." Limiting the number of options helps contribute the right data to aggregators, which often limit the types of licences allowed in their portal. This label could also be generated automatically based on the licence authority ID.	

46.	Field	Image rights: licence authority ID	Core
	RDF	dc:license , xmpRights:WebStatement	

Value	URI (limited set)
Example	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300055598
Note	Full web address of the licence of the image. Limiting the number of options helps contribute the right data to aggregators, which often limit the types of licences allowed in their portal.

47.

Field	Background: related images or objects	Additional
RDF	dc:relation	
Value	URI	
Example	<i>No sample record online (yet)</i>	
Note	Related images help users explore the archive. Related images could also be produced automatically based on, for example, Iconclass similarity. Using full URIs allows your data to travel to other repositories if necessary.	

48.

Field	Background: internal image or object notes	Additional
RDF	photoshop:Instructions	
Value	string	
Example	Image used to provide sample metadata in the recommendations for the digital resources of the Corpus Vitrearum International.	
Note	Hidden or unpublishable metadata field to be used throughout the editorial process or for information not covered by the other fields.	

49.

Field	Background: image or object bibliography	Additional
RDF	dc:source	
Value	URI or string	
Example	Isabelle Lecocq and Yvette Vanden Bemden. <i>The Stained Glass of Herkenrode Abbey</i> . Oxford University Press, 2021. Corpus Vitrearum (Great Britain) Monograph Series, vol. VII.	
Note	This field often contains bibliographic data as a string with new lines that indicate the start of the next bibliographic information. In an advanced scenario, using URIs or connecting this field to a dedicated bibliographic data model can help provide bibliographic data in a format that is less dependent on a specific citation style.	

Appendix 2: Metadata Comparison Chart

Caveat. The following table lists and compares a few general characteristics as well the metadata used in the annotation of images and objects in digital projects in Belgium, Germany, Great Britain, France, Poland, Portugal, and Switzerland. While members of the DU took great care when they contributed their data, this was done **across multiple languages** and may not always provide an exact match, let alone an identical data format.

	'13	'24	Germany	Switzerland	Great Britain	France	Portugal	Belgium	Poland
Setup			One dataset per image (XMP in TIFF), converted to and complimented by data tables when imported into TYPO3 frontend	Set of data tables in FileMaker with an object record at the centre, deployed to custom web software	Set of data tables in a custom web software with an image record at the centre, JPG2000 images	Data table in Dspace with an image record at the centre, migration to Heurist in the works	Linked open data repository based on MediaWiki with object records at the centre, interface customisations	Object records, often with several images, published on a national database for cultural heritage	?
Last edit of the data in this table			Updated in March 2023, object records to be added by a 2024 relaunch	Latest adjustments in December 2022, to be changed significantly	To be absorbed into an existing Arachne instance with a different data model in 2024	Being migrated from Dspace to Heurist and Nakala as of 2024	First prototype developed in 2023 (data from 2023), development continuing in 2024	Data from 2023, own thesauri and authority files to be published in the future	Data from the 2013 table, information may be outdated
No. of publ. image records			8,500	7,000	30,000	13,000	varies depending on the number of images per object record (currently around 40 images)	11,000	?
No. of publ. object records			-	6,000	-	-	around 15 sample object records with associated images (2,000 planned)	4,000	?
Technology									
Image file formats			TIFF, JPEG (frontend)	JPEG	JPEG2000	JPEG	png, gif, jpg, jpeg, webp, jfif, pdf, tif	TIFF, JPEG (frontend)	?
Metadata storage			XMP in TIFF files using ExifTool	FileMaker	MySQL, XML experiments	Dspace	MediaWiki (MySQL)	Relational database	?
Frontend			TYPO3, custom extensions	custom	custom	custom?	MediaWiki	BALaT KIK-IRPA (national database)	?
APIs and Linked Open Data			JSON-LD, RDF, LIDO	JSON-LD	?	?	JSON-LD, RDF	IIIF, XML, CSV, etc.	?
Licences			CC0 (metadata), CC BY-NC (images)	?	?	?	custom	custom	?
General									
Identifier	■	■	iri (assigned on import)	vitrails:numderef (Referenznummer)	PHOTODATA: CVMA inv. no.	id (automatic)	id (not currently exposed)	object number	-
Image title	■	■	dc:title (string)	Image.titre (Titel)	-	title (automatic)	-	-	-
Object title			dc:relation (string)	vitrails:titre (Titel)	WINDOW: Named window	-	Dc:title	title/name of the window	Bezeichnung der Glasmalerei
Object authority ID		□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Description	■	□	-	dc:description_rt (Beschreibung, Richtext)	-	cactheo.description.iconographie	Dc:description	-	Geschichte der Glasmalerei
Research			-	vitrails:recherches (Forschung)	-	-	-	-	Konservatorische Dokumentation
Genre	■	■	dc:type (string)	vitrails:type (Art des Objektes)	FORM: Form type	cactheo.type.techniqueArtistique (no longer necessary, created when three databases were supposed to be unified)	Dc:type	type of object	-
Subgenre			-	vitrails:categorie (Unterbegriff)	-	-	-	-	-
Category notes			-	-	FORM: Notes (internal)	-	-	-	-
Tags or collections			-	vitrails:numdiv (Inventar)	-	-	edm:datasetName (name of the collection)	-	-
Current and former location of object									
Continent			lptc4xmpExt:WorldRegion (string)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Country	■	■	lptc4xmpExt:CountryName (string)	Batiment.pay (Land)	- (see HISTORY fields below)	cactheo.coverage.spatialPays	Edm:country	country	-
Region or state	■	■	lptc4xmpExt:ProvinceState (string)	Batiment.salsah:canton (Kanton)	-	-	State/Region	state/region	Provinz
County			-	Batiment.arrondissement (Verwaltungskreis)	LOCATION: County (to 1974)	cactheo.coverage.spatialDepartement	-	-	Wojewodschaft, Landkreis, Gemeinde
Bailiwick			-	Batiment.district (Amtsbezirk)	-	-	-	-	-
Ecclesiastical administration unit			-	-	-	-	-	-	Diözese / Provinz / Dekanat
City or town	■	■	lptc4xmpExt:City (string)	Batiment.localite (Gemeinde)	LOCATION: Place	cactheo.coverage.spatialVille	City	city/town	Ort
Building	■	■	lptc4xmpExt:Sublocation (string)	Batiment.nom (Name)	LOCATION: Site/Monument	-	Building	institution	Name und Lage des Gebäudes, Nummer des Anhangs* / Adresse
Building authority ID		■	lptc4xmpExt:LocationId (uri, Geonames)	Batiment.geonamecode (GeoNames Code)	-	-	Geographic Identifier - Edm:Place	-	-
Repository/depositary	■	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Address	■	-	-	Batiment.adresse (Adresse)	-	-	- (see identifier below)	-	- (see building above)
Postcode			-	Batiment.plz (Postleitzahl)	-	-	- (see identifier below)	-	-
Latitude	■	■	exif:GPSLatitude (floating-point number)	Batiment.coordonne (Koordinaten)	LOCATION: NGR (National Grid Reference)	-	Edm:currentLocation	location	-
Longitude	■	■	exif:GPSLongitude (floating-point number)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Building info			-	Batiment.informationsbatiment (Informationen über das Gebäude)	-	-	-	-	Beschreibung des Gebäudes
Building dedication			-	-	LOCATION: Dedication/Institution	cactheo.coverage.edificeDenomination	-	-	Patrozinium
Building type			-	-	LOCATION: Building type (current)	cactheo.coverage.edificeType	-	-	Art des Sakralgebäude
Building type (former)			-	-	LOCATION: Building type (former)	-	-	-	-
Building no. in national cultural-heritage register			-	-	-	-	-	-	Nummer im Denkmalschutzregister
Building ground plan			- (currently in a separate data model)	-	LOCATION: Ground plan reference	-	-	-	Grundriss des Gebäudes
Building ground plan source			-	-	LOCATION: Ground plan source	-	-	-	-
Building ground plan caption			-	-	LOCATION: Ground plan caption	-	-	-	-
Building record author and date			-	Batiment.auteurnotice (BearbeiterIn und Erfassungsdatum)	-	-	-	-	Feldforschung - Datum und Ausfühler

	'13	'24	Germany	Switzerland	Great Britain	France	Portugal	Belgium	Poland
Building inventory language			-	Batiment.language (Inventarsprache)	-	-	-	-	-
Building notes			-	Batiment.notesinternes (Interne Bemerkungen)	-	-	-	-	Geschichte des Gebäudes
Building oeuvre			-	-	-	-	-	-	Anzahl der Glasmalereien und Charakteristik des Bestandes
Building image			-	Batiment.fotoprimaire (Hauptbild)	-	-	-	-	-
Building image (secondary)			-	Batiment.fotosecondaire (Ergänzendes Foto)	-	-	-	-	-
Building internal identifier			-	Batiment.idstr (Kennzeichnung)	-	-	-	-	-
Current location (internal ID)			-	vitrails:localisationid (Aktueller Standort)	-	-	-	-	-
Former locations (internal ID)			-	vitrails:localisationorigineid (Code localisation d'origine)	-	-	-	-	-
Former locations (names)	■	(s.a.)	cvma:FormerLocation (list, string)	vitrails:localisationorigine (Localisation d'origine)	-	-	Former/original locations	- (former locations to be added soon)	-
Former locations IDs			cvma:FormerLocationIds (list, uri, Geonames)	- (see building ID above)	-	-	Identifiers of original/former locations	-	-
Former locations (notes)			-	vitrails:localisationoriginecomment (Commentaire sur localisation d'origine)	-	-	-	-	-
Associated locations			-	vitrails:linkedloc (Verknüpfter Standort)	ARCHIVE: Archive name	-	-	-	-
Associated locations notes			-	vitrails:linkedloccomment (Kommentar zu verknüpfter Standort)	-	-	-	-	-
Window									
Location in the building	■	■	cvma:PartOfBuilding (string)	vitrails:depot (Aktueller Lagerraum)	WINDOW: General part of church	cactheo.coverage.situationEmplacementPrecis	-	-	-
Location in the building (alternative)			-	-	WINDOW: Subsidiary part of church	cactheo.coverage.situationEmplacement	-	-	-
Description of window location			-	-	WINDOW: Window description	cactheo.coverage.situationLocalisation	-	-	Standort der Glasmalerei innerhalb des Gebäudes
Secular description of window location			-	-	WINDOW: Secular setting	-	-	-	-
Name of chapel			-	-	WINDOW: Named chapel	-	-	-	-
Previous parts of the building			-	vitrails:depotprec (Ehemalige Lagerräume)	-	-	-	-	-
Storage type			-	vitrails:emplacement (Lage)	-	-	-	-	-
Window direction	■	■	cvma:Direction (string)	-	WINDOW: Orientation	-	Direction	-	-
Window number	■	■	cvma:Pane (string)	-	WINDOW: CVMA window number	cactheo.coverage.situationLocalisationPrecise	Window number	-	-
Panel row	■	■	cvma:Row (string)	-	PANELUNIT: CVMA panel number	-	Row	-	-
Panel column	■	■	cvma:Column (string)	-	-	-	Column	-	-
Object rights									
Inventory number	■		-	Ouvre.numdiv (Inventarnummer)	PANELUNIT: Museum registration number	-	Dc:identifier (in collection)	inventory number	-
Inventory language			-	Ouvre.language (Inventarsprache)	-	-	-	-	-
Owner	■	□	-	vitrails:proprietaire (BesitzerIn)	-	-	Owner's name	-	-
Owner (internal)			-	-	-	-	Owner's identifier	-	-
Previous owner			-	vitrails:proprietaireante (Vorbesitzer)	-	-	-	-	-
Seller			-	vitrails:donateurext (Schenker / Verkäufer)	-	-	-	-	-
Seller (internal)			-	vitrails:donateurs (Schenker / Verkäufer intern)	-	-	-	-	-
Date of receipt			-	vitrails:dateentree (Eingangsdatum)	-	-	-	-	-
Acquisition type			-	vitrails:modeacquisition (Erwerbsart)	-	-	-	-	-
Copyright holder		□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rights string		□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Licence name		□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Licence authority ID		□	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dimensions									
Height	■	■	cvma:ObjectHeight (string)	vitrails:dimensions (Masse)	-	-	dcterms:extent	height	Maße
Width			■ cvma:ObjectWidth (string)	-	-	-	width		
Diameter			■ cvma:ObjectDiameter (string)	-	-	-	diameter		
Condition									
Technique	■	□	-	vitrails:technique (Technik)	-	-	Production technique	technique	-
Materials	■	□	-	vitrails:materieux (Materialien)	-	-	-	materials	-
Description of current condition			-	vitrails:etatconservation (Zustandsbewertung)	-	-	current state of conservation	intervention file	Erhaltungszustand / konservatorische Bemerkungen

	'13	'24	Germany	Switzerland	Great Britain	France	Portugal	Belgium	Poland
Restoration history		<input type="checkbox"/>	cvma:RestorationHistory (string, gradually replaced by a restoration event list, s.b.)	vitrails:etatrestauration (Erhaltungszustand und Restaurierungen)	-	cactheo.note_oeuvre	restoration and conservation history (pdf)	- (restoration history to be added soon)	Konservierungen der Glasmalerei
Restauration date (approx.)			cvma:RestorationCircaDate (list, string)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Restauration date start			cvma:RestorationDateStart (list, date)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Restauration date end			cvma:RestorationDateEnd (list, date)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Restauration event			cvma:RestorationEvent (list, string)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pane/window lost			cvma:PanelLost (bool)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Creation date and events									
Exhibitions			-	vitrails:expositions (Ausstellungen)	-	-	-	-	-
Fragment described			-	-	HISTORY: Part	-	-	-	-
Fragment status			-	-	HISTORY: Status	-	-	-	-
Creation date (approximate)			lptc4xmpExt:AOCircaDateCreated (string)	vitrails:datation (Datierung)	HISTORY: Date	cactheo.coverage.temporalChiffre	-	approximate creation date	Entstehungsdatum
Creation date (century)			-	-	-	cactheo.coverage.temporalSiecle	-	-	-
Creation date start	■	■	cvma:AgeDeterminationStart (date)	vitrails:datepostquem (Anfangsdatum)	HISTORY: Century from	-	Date of origin including standard beginning and standard end	date start	-
Creation date end	■	■	cvma:AgeDeterminationEnd (date)	vitrails:dateantequem (Enddatum)	HISTORY: Century to	-	-	date end	-
Creation location			-	vitrails:lieudeprod (Herstellungsort)	HISTORY: Site of provenance	-	-	-	-
Creation location (country)			-	-	HISTORY: Country of provenance	-	-	-	-
Creation note			-	vitrails:lieudeprodcommentaire (Kommentar zum Herstellungsort)	HISTORY: Notes (internal)	-	-	-	-
Creation note (alternative)			-	-	HISTORY: Description (internal)	-	-	-	-
Entity									
Artist (internal ID)			-	vitrails:artisteid (Künstler-Id) / artists:id	-	-	-	-	-
Note on artist			-	vitrails:artistecommentaire (Kommentar zur/zum Künstlerin)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist internal identifier			- (s.b.)	Artiste.idstr (Kennzeichnung)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist SIKART		(s.b.)	-	Artiste.liensikart (Link zu SIKART)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist GND		(s.b.)	-	Artiste.liengnd (Verknüpfung zur GND)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist Wikidata		(s.b.)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Artist DHS			-	Artiste.liendhs (Verknüpfung mit DHS)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist name	■	(s.b.) - (s.b.)	-	Artiste.nom (Name)	-	creator	Dc:Creator	creator	Entwerfer
Artist name (alternative)			-	Artiste.formrejetee (Namensvarianten)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist biography			-	Artiste.bio (Biografische Daten)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist biographical data			-	Artiste.datevie (Lebensdaten)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist website			-	Artiste.siteweb (Webseite)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist record author and date			-	Artiste.auteurnotice (BearbeiterIn und Erfassungsdatum)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist inventory language			-	Artiste.language (Inventarsprache)	-	-	-	-	-
Artist notes (internal)			-	Artiste.notesinternes (Interne Bemerkungen)	-	-	-	-	-
Other artists			-	-	-	-	Cartoon designer	-	-
Glass painter	■	(s.b.) - (s.b.)	-	-	-	-	-	-	Ausführer
Workshop			-	-	-	-	-	place of production	-
Note on workshop			- (s.b.)	vitrails:ateliercommentaire (Kommentar zur Werkstatt)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop identifier			-	vitrails:atelierid (Werkstatt-Id)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop name	■	(s.b.) - (s.b.)	-	Atelier.nom (Name)	HISTORY: Firm	-	Workshop	-	-
Workshop name (alternative)			-	Atelier.formrejetee (Namensvarianten)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop info			-	Atelier.infoatelier (Informationen über die Werkstatt)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop activity			-	Atelier.dateactivite (Werkstatt tätig von – bis)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop website			-	Atelier.siteweb (Webseite)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop record author and date			-	Atelier.auteurnotice (BearbeiterIn und Erfassungsdatum)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop inventory language			-	Atelier.language (Inventarsprache)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop notes (internal)			-	Atelier.notesinternes (Interne Bemerkungen)	-	-	-	-	-
Restorer name			- (s.b.)	-	-	- (added in the "creator" field along with the artist)	-	-	-
Donor name	■	(s.b.) - (s.b.)	-	vitrails:donateurs (Stifter)	-	cactheo.contributor_donateur	-	-	-
Entity names		■	cvma:EntityName (list, string)	- (s.a.)	- (s.a.)	- (s.a.)	- (s.a.)	-	-

	'13	'24	Germany	Switzerland	Great Britain	France	Portugal	Belgium	Poland
Entity identifiers			cvma:Entity/Identifier (list, uri)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Entity authority IDs		<input type="checkbox"/>	entity authority IDs (separate data table)	- (s.a.)	-	-	-	-	-
Entity roles		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cvma:EntityRole (list, string)	- (s.a.)	-	-	-	-	-
Subject									
Iconclass/iconography authority ID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cvma:IconclassNotation (list, string)	vitrails:iconclass (Iconclass Code)	-	cactheo.iconographie_scene (Sancti)	iconclass notation	-	-
Iconclass/iconography label			cvma:IconclassDescription (list, string)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Iconclass/iconography keywords	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	keywords (assigned on import)	-	-	-	iconclass keywords	-	-
Iconography cycle			-	-	-	cactheo.iconographie_cycle (Sancti)	-	-	-
Christian iconography			-	-	-	-	-	Christian iconography	Historische Ikonographie
Pictorial representation			-	-	-	cactheo.description_caracteristique: décor figuré	-	subject	-
Ornament representation			-	-	-	cactheo.description_caracteristique: ornaments	-	-	-
Music representation			-	-	-	cactheo.description_caracteristique: music instrument/singing	-	-	-
Heraldry representation			-	vitrails:heraldique (Heraldik)	-	cactheo.description_caracteristique: héraldique	-	-	-
Inscription	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	-	vitrails:inscriptions (Inschriften)	-	cactheo.description_caracteristique: inscriptions	-	inscriptions	-
Signature	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	-	vitrails:signature (Signatur)	-	-	Signature	-	Signaturen
Image									
Image extent			-	-	PANELUNIT: Panel description	-	Images descriptions	-	-
Image colour			color (assigned on import)	-	PHOTODATA: Colour/black and white	cactheo.format_colorimetrie	-	-	-
Image inventory identifier	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		dc:identifier (string)	Image.nomphoto (Name der Fotografie)	PHOTODATA: Photo reference	cactheo.identifier_cote	-	cliché number	-
Image inventory identifier (additional)			-	-	-	cactheo.identifier_fichier	-	-	-
Photographic process		<input type="checkbox"/>	cvma:PhotographicType (string)	Image.informations (Informationen)	PANELUNIT: Face	-	Photographic process	-	-
Source image type			lpto4xmpExt:DigitalSourceType (string)	-	PHOTODATA: Photo format	cactheo.format_support_origine	Digital image source	type of object (argentic, digital)	-
Photographic context		<input type="checkbox"/>	cvma:PhotographicContext (string)	-	PHOTODATA: Where taken	cactheo.description_lieu_prise_de_vue	Photographic context	-	-
Object condition when photo was taken			-	-	PHOTODATA: Condition taken	cactheo.note_technique	-	-	-
Location where ex situ photo was taken			-	-	PHOTODATA: Site taken	-	-	-	-
Creation date	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		xmp:CreateDate (date)	Image.datephoto (Aufnahmedatum)	PHOTODATA: Year taken	cactheo.date_prise_de_vue	Photo creation date	date (year)	-
Image date (qualifier)			-	-	PHOTODATA: Year qualifier	-	-	-	-
Location of original			-	-	PHOTODATA: Photo location	-	-	-	-
Location of negative			-	-	PHOTODATA: Negative location (redundant)	-	-	-	-
Identifier of negative			-	-	PHOTODATA: Negative reference (redundant)	-	-	-	-
Image rights									
Rights managed or public domain			xmpRights:Marked (bool)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Photographer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	dc:creator (string)	- (see rights string)	-	photographer	Image author	photographer	Autor des Fotos
Digitised by			-	-	-	cactheo.contributor_numerisateur	-	-	-
Digitisation date			-	-	-	cactheo.date_numerisation	-	-	-
Owner	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	xmpRights:Owner (string)	Image.copyright (Copyright)	PHOTODATA: Copyright	cactheo.collection_particuliere	Holder of rights	copyright	-
Publisher		<input type="checkbox"/>	dc:publisher (string)	-	-	publisher	Publisher	-	-
Rights string			<input type="checkbox"/> photoshop:Credit (string)	Image.creditphoto (Fotonachweise)	-	autorisation de diffusion	-	-	-
Licence name		<input type="checkbox"/>	xmpRights:UsageTerms (string)	-	-	-	License type	-	-
Licence authority ID		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	xmpRights:WebStatement (uri)	-	-	-	License description	-	-
Background: representations									
Variants (format)			derivatives (assigned on import)	-	-	cactheo.format_support_image	-	-	-
Variants (size)			-	-	-	cactheo.format_resolution_image	-	-	-
Model or sketch			-	vitrails:modele (Vorlage)	-	-	-	-	-
Main image			-	vitrails:fotoprimaire (Hauptbild)	-	-	-	-	-
Additional images			-	vitrails:fotosecondaire (Ergänzendes Foto)	-	-	-	-	-
Other images			-	vitrails:autrephoto (Referenzen zu weiteren Fotos)	-	-	-	-	-

	'13	'24	Germany	Switzerland	Great Britain	France	Portugal	Belgium	Poland
Related images or objects		<input type="checkbox"/>	related (assigned on import)	vitrails:noticees (Verknüpfte Objekte)	-	handle_id_child and handle_id_parent (does not work as we wished it would)	historic related images	-	-
Background: notes									
Publishing status			cvma:PublishingStatus (bool)	-	PHOTODATA: Web published	rights	-	-	-
Unresolved linked records			-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Object notes		<input type="checkbox"/>	-	-	WINDOW: Notes	-	-	-	Bemerkungen
Image notes			photoshop:instructions (string)	-	PHOTODATA: Notes	Notes: technical information	-	-	-
Object record author			-	vitrails:auteurnotice (BearbeiterIn und Erfassungsdatum)	-	-	Registry Author	-	-
Object record date			-	-	-	-	Registry Date	-	-
Image record author			-	Image.auteurnotice (BearbeiterIn und Erfassungsdatum)	-	contributor_author	-	-	Kartenautor
Image record date			-	-	-	date de la notice and date_updated	-	-	Erstellungsdatum der Karte
Image inventory language			-	language_id (Inventarsprache)	-	language_iso	-	-	-
Image migration info			-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Background: paratexts									
Paratext medium			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: medium	-	-	-	-
Paratext artist			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: creator	-	-	-	-
Paratext inscription			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: inscription	-	-	-	-
Paratext date			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: date	-	-	-	-
Paratext measurements			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: measurements	-	-	-	-
Paratext owner			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: copyright	-	-	-	-
Paratext location			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: location	-	-	-	-
Paratext location number			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: location reference	-	-	-	-
Paratext publication			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: publication	-	-	-	-
Paratext publication number			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: publication reference	-	-	-	-
Paratext notes (internal)			-	-	INTERMEDIUM: Notes	-	-	-	-
Background: bibliography									
Volume of the book series			cvma:Volume (string)	-	PANELUNIT: Published source	-	-	-	-
Page/figure number in the book series			cvma:Figure (string)	-	PANELUNIT: Published source reference	-	-	-	-
Catalogue volume			-	-	FORM: Quarry reference	-	-	-	-
Catalogue number			-	-	FORM: Quarry number	-	-	-	-
Catalogue volume (additional)			-	-	FORM: Roundel reference	-	-	-	-
Catalogue number (additional)			-	-	FORM: Roundel number	-	-	-	-
Documentation			-	vitrails:documentations (Nachweisakten)	PANELUNIT: Notes (internal)	-	laboratorial pdf or url (associated docs. on the piece)	-	-
Image or object bibliography		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	- (s.a.)	vitrails:bibliographie (Literatur)	- (s.a.)	-	bibliography text field with several possible entries	bibliography	Literatur
Building bibliography			-	Batiment.bibliographie (Literatur)	-	-	-	-	Grundlegende Literatur und archivalische Quellen
Artist bibliography			-	Artiste.bibliographie (Literatur)	-	-	-	-	-
Workshop bibliography			-	Atelier.bibliographie (Literatur)	-	-	-	-	-